

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

1.1.1 IMAGE PROCESSING:

Image Processing is any form of processing for which the input is an image or a series of images or videos, such as photographs. The output of image processing can be either an image or a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image.

Image processing, the manipulation of images by computer, is a relatively recent development in terms of man's ancient fascination with visual stimuli. It has been applied to practically every type of images with varying degree of success. The inherent subjective appeal of pictorial displays attracts perhaps a disproportionate amount of attention from the scientists and also from the layman. Digital image processing like other glamour fields, suffers from myths, misconceptions, misunderstandings and misinformation. It is a vast umbrella under which fall diverse aspects of optics, electronics, mathematics, photography graphics and computer technology. It is truly a multidisciplinary endeavour ploughed with imprecise jargon. Several factors combine to indicate a lively future for digital image processing. A major factor is the declining cost of computer equipment. Several new technological trends promise to further promote digital image processing. These include parallel processing made practical by low cost microprocessors, and the use of charge coupled devices (CCDs) for digitizing, storage during processing and display and large low cost of image storage arrays. Image processing is a method to perform some operations on

an image, in order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it. It is a type of signal processing in which input is an image and output may be image or characteristics/features associated with that image. Nowadays, image processing is among rapidly growing technologies. It forms core research area within engineering and computer science disciplines too.

Image processing basically includes the following three steps:

- Importing the image via image acquisition tools.
- Analysing and manipulating the image.
- Output in which result can be altered image or report that is based on image analysis.

There are two types of methods used for image processing namely, analogue and digital image processing. Analogue image processing can be used for the hard copies like printouts and photographs. Image analysts use various fundamentals of interpretation while using these visual techniques. Digital image processing techniques help in manipulation of the digital images by using computers. The three general phases that all types of data have to undergo while using digital technique are pre-processing, enhancement, and display, information extract.

1.1.2 IMAGE FILE SIZE:

Image file size is expressed as the number of bytes that increases with the number of pixels composing an image, and the color depth of the pixels. The greater the number of rows and columns, the greater the image resolution, and the larger the file. Also, each pixel of an image increases in size when its

color depth increases, an 8-bit pixel (1 byte) stores 256 colors, a 24-bit pixel (3 bytes) stores 16 million colors, the latter known as true color. Image compression uses algorithms to decrease the size of a file. High resolution cameras produce large image files, ranging from hundreds of kilobytes to megabytes, per the camera & resolution and the image-storage format capacity. High resolution digital cameras record 12 megapixel (1MP = 1,000,000 pixels / 1 million) images, or more, in true color. For example, an image recorded by a 12 MP camera; since each pixel uses 3 bytes to record true color, the uncompressed image would occupy 36,000,000 bytes of memory, a great amount of digital storage for one image, given that cameras must record and store many images to be practical. Faced with large file sizes, both within the camera and a storage disc, image file formats were developed to store such large images.

1.1.3 IMAGE FILE FORMATS

Image file formats are standardized means of organizing and storing images. This entry is about digital image formats used to store photographic and other images. Image files are composed of either pixel or vector (geometric) data that are rasterized to pixels when displayed (with few exceptions) in a vector graphic display. Including proprietary types, there are hundreds of image file types. The PNG, JPEG, and GIF formats are most often used to display images on the Internet.

In addition to straight image formats, Metafile formats are portable formats which can include both raster and vector information. The metafile format is an intermediate format. Most Windows applications open metafiles and then save them in their own native format.

1.2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Text recognition in images is a research area which attempts to develop a computer system with the ability to automatically read the text from images. These days there is a huge demand in storing the information available in paper documents format in to a computer storage disk and then later reusing this information by searching process. One simple way to store information from these paper documents in to computer system is to first scan the documents and then store them as images. But to reuse this information it is very difficult to read the individual contents and searching the contents form these documents line-by-line and word-by-word. The challenges involved in this the font characteristics of the characters in paper documents and quality of images. Due to these challenges, computer is unable to recognize the characters while reading them. Thus there is a need of character recognition mechanisms to perform Document Image Analysis (DIA) which transforms documents in paper format to electronic format. In this paper we have discuss method for text recognition from images. The objective of this paper is to recognition of text from image for better understanding of the reader by using particular sequence of different processing module.

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

The identification of character or word in an image is not an easy thing. The exact identification of character is not possible by the machine using the camera. The reason behind this is for the distance between the camera and the object leads to change in the size of the character.to overcome this we are going for the single character identification this results in the increasing the efficiency of the system.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

PAPER 1:

Title: Text Detection and Removal from Image using Inpainting with Smoothing

Author: D. R. Patil, Priyanka Delip Wagh

Year: 2015

Description:

In this paper we have implemented a two stage frame work to remove unwanted text from images: first stage is to detect text from image and second stage is to remove that text using method of inpainting. To detect text, text localization and extraction is carried out followed by method of inpainting to fill the holes generated in image using surrounding region. To bring more efficiency in text detection smoothing works better. With the use of feature extraction, stroke filtering and centroid processing text detection is performed. Color histogram processing is carried out to carry clearer filtering of text components from other image components. In last stage, the text holes generated are filled with appropriate information present in same image using nearest matching neighborhood inpainting.

To generate visually plausible region filling results, smoothing is carried out on the selected filled patches. We tested the implementation using different images, and compared the results of smoothing with results of implementation without smoothing. Experimental results show improved PSNR due to smoothing.

PAPER 2:

Title: Connected Component Based Approach for Text Extraction from Color Image

Author: Tania Mallick, Kamrul Hasa Talukder

Year: 2014

Description:

Image based text extraction is one of the fastest growing research areas in the field of multimedia technology. The extraction of text from a complex or more colorful images is a challenging problem. Text data present in images contains useful information for habitual explanation, indexing, and structuring of images. Extraction of this information involves detection, localization, tracking, extraction, enhancement, and recognition of the text from a given image. For fast extracting text from images, we have proposed a connected component based approach which identifies more accurately for small or large texts in the image. The text extraction process starts with conversion of the color image to gray scale image and then it converts the gray scale image into a binary image. Then each text region is marked and the text is extracted from the image. Finally, the extracted text is written into another gray scale image. The experimental results demonstrate that the performance of the proposed method is superior compared to some recent approaches.

PAPER 3:

Title: Automatic Text Detection Using Morphological Operations and Inpainting

Author: Khyati Vaghela , Narendra Patel

Year:2014

Description:

Image inpainting is the process of restoring the lost or damaged regions or modifying the image contents imperceptibly. It refers to the process of filling-in missing data in a designated region of the visual input. In this paper,the technique presented is for detection and removal of text from images. The system detects text using morphological operations, connected component labelling and a set of selection criteria which helps to filter out non text regions. This system could enhance and return a good looking photograph using a technique called image inpainting. Image inpainting modify and fill the missing area in an image in an undetectable way, by an observer not familiar with the original image. The technique can be used to reconstruct image damage due to dirt, scratches, overlaid text etc. So,the resultant image is the image with only texts. Text Inpainting is done in two steps:

- The first step detects the text region automatically, without user interaction
- The second step the text is removed from the image using exemplar based Inpainting algorithm.

PAPER 4:

Title: SnooperText: A text detection system for automatic indexing of urban scenes

Author: Rodrigo Minetto , Nicolas Thome , Matthieu Cord , Neucimar J. Leite, Jorge Stolfi

Year:2013

Description:

SNOOPERTEXT, an original detector for textual information embedded in photos of building façades (such as names of stores, products and services) that we developed for the iTowns urban geographic information project. SNOOPERTEXT locates candidate characters by using toggle-mapping image segmentation and character/non-character classification based on shape descriptors. The candidate characters are then grouped to form either candidate words or candidate text lines. These candidate regions are then validated by a text/non-text classifier using a HOG-based descriptor specifically tuned to single-line text regions. These operations are applied at multiple image scales in order to suppress irrelevant detail in character shapes and to avoid the use of overly large kernels in the segmentation. SNOOPERTEXT outperforms other published state-of-the-art text detection algorithms on standard image benchmarks. We also describe two metrics to evaluate the end-to-end performance of text extraction systems, and show that the use of SNOOPERTEXT as a pre-filter significantly improves the performance of a general-purpose OCR algorithm when applied to photos of urban scenes.

PAPER 5:

Title: Auto Scene Text Detection Based on Edge and Color Features

Author: Xiaodong Huang, Kehua Liu, Lishang Zhu

Year: 2012

Description:

In this paper we present a novel approach to detecting scene text based on the edge and color features. With the rapid growth of video data, there is an urgent demand for video semantic analysis, retrieval and annotation. Text contains semantic information and can contribute significantly to video retrieval and understanding.

Firstly, because the character edge feature is not sensitive to the luminance changes, we extract the edge features to locate the candidate text region coarsely.

Secondly, according to the text row character will keep similar color, we use the K-means clustering to extract color feature and locate the candidate text regions accurately. . The candidate characters are then grouped to form either candidate words or candidate text lines. These candidate regions are then validated by a text/non-text classifier using a HOG-based descriptor specifically tuned to single-line text regions. Finally, we use a trained SVM classifier to distinguish the text region from non-text region in these candidate regions. Experimental results show that our algorithm performs well for detecting scene text with various color, font-size and text alignment.

PAPER 6:

Title: Word Spotting and Recognition with Embedded Attributes

Author: Jon Almazan, Albert Gordo, Alicia Forn 'es, Ernest Valveny

Year: 2012.

Description:

This article addresses the problems of word spotting and word recognition on images. In word spotting, the goal is to find all instances of a query word in a dataset of images. In recognition, the goal is to recognize the content of the word image, usually aided by a dictionary or lexicon. We describe an approach in which both word images and text strings are embedded in a common vectorial subspace. This is achieved by a combination of label embedding and attributes learning, and a common subspace regression. In this subspace, images and strings that represent the same word are close together, allowing one to cast recognition and retrieval tasks as a nearest neighbor problem. Contrary to most other existing methods, our representation has a fixed length, is low dimensional, and is very fast to compute and, especially, to compare. We test our approach on four public datasets of both handwritten documents and natural images showing results comparable or better than the state-of-the-art on spotting and recognition tasks. In this paper we consider two problems related to text understanding: word spotting and word recognition. In word spotting, the goal is to find all instances of a query word in a dataset of images. In word recognition, the goal is to obtain a transcription of the query word image.

PAPER 7:

Title: Novel Approach for Text Extraction from Natural Images Using ISEF Edge Detection

Author: Sanjay Shah, Chintan Modi, Manisha Patel

Year: 2011

Description:

In this paper, novel approach for text extraction is presented. In computer vision research area, text is very important in images. Here we use edge based extraction of text using ISEF (infinite symmetrical edge filter). ISEF is optimal edge detector which gives accurate results for text in images. The candidate characters are then grouped to form either candidate words or candidate text lines. These candidate regions are then validated by a text/non-text classifier using a HOG-based descriptor specifically tuned to single-line text regions. Text extraction involves detection, localization, tracking and enhancement. Large numbers of technique have been proposed for the text extraction. Our aim is to present robust technique for text extraction. Recent research area of image processing has much interest in content retrieval. It can be derived in the perceptual and semantic content. Perceptual includes color, intensity, shape and texture and semantic includes objects, events, and their relations. Texts are also easily and clearly describe the contents of an image. Since the text data can be embedded in an image. Up till now it has been extracted by two basic techniques. That are edge and connected component based technique. A text extraction system receives an input in the form of an image or a sequence of images.

PAPER 8:

Title: Robust text detection in natural images with edge-enhanced maximally stable extremal regions

Author: Huizhong Chen¹, Sam S. Tsai¹, Georg Schroth, David M. Chen¹, Radek Grzeszczuk, Bernd Girod

Year: 2011.

Description

Detecting text in natural images is an important prerequisite. In this paper, we propose a novel text detection algorithm, which employs edge-enhanced Maximally Stable Extremal Regions as basic letter candidates. These candidates are then filtered using geometric and stroke width information to exclude non-text objects. Letters are paired to identify text lines, which are subsequently separated into words. We evaluate our system using the ICDAR competition dataset and our mobile document database. The experimental results demonstrate the excellent performance of the proposed method.

Mobile visual search has gained popular interest with the increasing availability of high-performance, low-cost camera-phones. In recent years, visual search systems have been developed for applications such as product recognition and landmark recognition. In these systems, local image features are extracted from images taken with a camera-phone and are matched to a large database using visual word indexing techniques.

PAPER 9:

Title: A Low Complexity Sign Detection and Text Localization Method for Mobile Applications

Author: Katherine L. Bouman, Golnaz Abdollahian, Mireille Boutin, Edward J. Delp

Year:2011

Description

A low complexity method for sign detection and text localization in natural images. This method is designed for mobile applications (e.g., unmanned or handheld devices) in which computational and energy resources are limited. No prior assumption is made regarding the text size, font, language, or character set. However, the text is assumed to be located on a homogeneous background using a contrasting color. We have deployed our method on a Nokia N800 cellular phone as part of a system for automatic detection and translation of outdoor signs. This handheld device is equipped with a 0.3-megapixel camera capable of acquiring images of outdoor signs that typically contain enough details for the sign to be readable by a human viewer. Our experiments show that the text of these images can be accurately localized within the device in a fraction of a second.

PAPER 10:

Title: Features Extraction for Text Detection and Localization

Author: Hinde, Driss, Abdellilah

Year:2010.

Description:

With the widely use of digital image, text location/detection is considered as a key part of the image text information extraction system. We have proposed a robust system for text detection in images. The proposed scheme uses a set of characteristics which are combined to build a large ones, it's based on texture features and connected components analysis. First, edge detection technique is used to detect all edges in the image, to preserve the most important structural features of that image by finding sharp contrasts, after that, we select all closed contours from detected edges. By the next we use texture information to discriminate text from non-text regions.

Finally,we verify regions in order to reduce false alarms and to generate valid text regions. Detecting text in natural images is an important prerequisite. In this paper, we propose a novel text detection algorithm, which em-ploys edge-enhanced Maximally Stable Extremal Regions as basic letter candidates. These candidates are then filtered using geometric and stroke width information to exclude non-text objects.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

The characters are segmented manually. The text in the image is detected by Optical Character Recognition. The image is not enhanced if the image quality is poor. Exact text is not detected when the image is of low quality. The image is based on 32 x 32 and its mostly done by Deep Neural Network. Without activation function, neural networks would not be able to learn and model complicated information such as audio, speech and images. Batch size defines the number of image samples that are propagated through the network. Batch size does influence training time and accuracy but there is no general rule for determining the optimal batch size. To investigate on how the accuracy and time usage are affected by the number of training iterations that the accuracy increases at the beginning from 1,000 iterations until 50,000 iterations. The accuracy converges after 50,000 iterations and no improvement . A deep convolutional neural network, the first layer will train itself to recognize very basic things like edges, the next layer will train itself to recognize collections of edges such as shapes, and subsequent layers.

3.1.1 DISADVANTAGES

- Sensitive to noise and it may generate error during detection.
- Computationally complex and Time consuming.
- Poor edge detection.
- Manual Segmentation.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is very efficient and it did not need any manual segmentation. The simple system Architecture of the proposed system makes very simple for the usage and implementation of the system. The proposed system does this by using preprocessing to enhance the image. The horizontal and vertical edge of the image can be detected by sobel operator. The preprocessing is based on 250x250 pixel size. The K-means clustering algorithm is used for grouping of the similar text. The partition of the character is done by using segmentation. Exact character is been identified by the morphological process.

The datasets are trained by the user and stored in the database. The RNN classifier compares the segmented text and trained dataset. After comparison if the trained data and the segmented text is same then the corresponding audio file is been given as the output. Unlike other neural network, RNNs can use their internal state (memory) to process sequences of inputs. This makes them applicable to tasks such as unsegmented, connected typed recognition or speech recognition. This proposed System can be used for visually impaired.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES

- This System is used for visually Impaired.
- Separating text from complex background images.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential.

Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are

- Economic feasibility
- Technical feasibility
- Social feasibility

3.3.1 Economic feasibility

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 Technical feasibility

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high

demands on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system. This technology supports the modern trends of technology. Easily accessible more secure technologies.

3.3.3 Social feasibility

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE :

Fig 4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

4.2 UML DIAGRAM

4.2 Use case Diagram

A usecase diagram is a type of behavioural diagram created from a use-case analysis. It is a set of scenarios that describing an interaction between a user and a system. A use case diagram displays the relationship among the actors and use cases.

Fig 4.2 Use case diagram

4.3 Sequence Diagram:

A sequence diagram shows object interactions arranged in time sequence. It depicts the objects and classes involved in the scenario and the sequence of messages exchanged between the objects needed to carry out the functionality of the scenario. Sequence diagrams are typically associated with use case realizations in the Logical View of the system under development. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called **event diagrams** or **event scenarios**.

Fig 4.3 Sequence diagram

4.4 Activity Diagram

Activity diagram are graphical representation of stepwise activities and actions with support for choices, iteration and concurrency. In the UML, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflow of components in a system. It is an graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency.

Fig 4.4 Activity diagram

4.5 Class Diagram

Class diagram is UML structure diagram which shows structure of the designed system at the level of classes and interfaces, shows their features constraints and relationships-associations, generalizations, dependencies ,etc. A class diagram in the UML is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, and the relationships between the classes.

Fig 4.5 Class diagram

4.6 Data flow Diagram

Data flow diagram is made up of a number of symbols, which represents system components. Most data flow modelling methods use four kinds of symbols. These symbols are used to represent four kinds of system components. Process, data stores, data flows and external entities. Processes are represented by circles in DFD. A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the flow of data through an information system. It differs from the flowchart as it shows the data flow instead of the control flow of the program. A data flow diagram can also be used for the visualization of data processing

4.6.1 Level 0

Fig 4.6 Data flow diagram Level 0

4.6.2 Level 1

Fig 4.7 Data flow diagram Level 1

4.6.3 Overall Data Flow Diagram

DFD consists of four major components: entities, process, data stores and data flow. This DFD shows the relation the user and the system and all the details are stored in database.

Fig 4.8 Overall Data Flow Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The requirement specification is a technical specification of requirements of the software products. It is the first step in the requirement analysis process, it lists the requirements of a particular software system including functional, performance and security requirements.

The requirements also provides usage scenario from a user, an operational and an administrative perspective. The purpose of software requirements specification is to provide a detailed overview of the software project, its parameter and goals. This describes the project target audience and its user interface, hardware and software requirements

5.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- Speaker

5.3 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- **OPERATING SYSTEM** :WINDOWS 7
- **SOFTWARE** : MATLAB 2014a and above versions
- **CODING LANGUAGE** : c, c++

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

MATLAB is a high-performance language for technical computing. It integrates computation, visualization, and programming in an easy-to-use environment where problems and solutions are expressed in familiar mathematical notation. MATLAB is an interactive system whose basic data element is an array that does not require dimensioning. This allows you to solve many technical computing problems, especially those with matrix and vector formulations, in a fraction of the time it would take to write a program in a scalar noninteractive language such as C or FORTRAN.

- Math and computation
- Algorithm development
- Modeling, simulation, and prototyping
- Data analysis, exploration, and visualization
- Scientific and engineering graphics
- Application development, including graphical user interface building

MATLAB features a family of application-specific solutions called toolboxes. Very important to most users of MATLAB, toolboxes allow you to learn and apply specialized technology. Toolboxes are comprehensive collections of MATLAB functions (M-files) that extend the MATLAB environment to solve particular classes of problems. Areas in which

toolboxes are available include signal processing, control systems, neural networks, fuzzy logic, wavelets, simulation, and many others.

This is a high-level matrix or array language with control flow statements, functions, data structures, input or output, and object-oriented programming features. It allows both programming in the small to rapidly create quick and dirty throw-away programs, and programming in the large to create complete large and complex application programs.

Functions

MATLAB provides a large number of standard elementary mathematical functions, including `abs`, `sqrt`, `exp`, and `sin`. Taking the square root or logarithm of a negative number is not an error; the appropriate complex result is produced automatically. MATLAB also provides many more advanced mathematical functions, including Bessel and gamma functions. Most of these functions accept complex arguments. For a list of more advanced mathematical and matrix functions, type `help specific function` `help element`.

Some of the functions, like `sqrt` and `sin`, are built-in. They are part of the MATLAB core so they are very efficient, but the computational details are not readily accessible. Other functions, like `gamma` and `sinh`, are implemented in M-files. You can see the code and even modify it if you want. Several special functions provide values of useful constants.

MATLAB uses conventional decimal notation, with an optional decimal point and leading plus or minus sign, for numbers. Scientific notation uses the letter `e` to specify a power-of-ten scale factor.

6.6.1:C LANGUAGE

C is a general-purpose, imperative computer programming language, supporting structured programming, lexical variable scope and recursion, while a static type system prevents many unintended operations. By design, C provides constructs that map efficiently to typical machine instructions, and therefore it has found lasting use in applications that had formerly been coded in assembly language, including operating systems, as well as various application software for computers ranging from supercomputers to embedded systems.

Like most imperative languages in the ALGOL tradition, C has facilities for structured programming and allows lexical variable scope and recursion, while a static type system prevents many unintended operations. In C, all executable code is contained within subroutines, which are called "functions" (although not in the strict sense of functional programming). Function parameters are always passed by value. Pass-by-reference is simulated in C by explicitly passing pointer values. C program source text is free-format, using the semicolon as a statement terminator and curly braces for grouping blocks of statements.

The C language also exhibits the following characteristics:

- There is a small, fixed number of keywords, including a full set of control flow primitives: `for`, `if/else`, `while`, `switch`, and `do/while`. User-defined names are not distinguished from keywords by any kind of sigil.
- There are a large number of arithmetical and logical operators, such as `+`, `+=`, `++`, `&`, `~`, etc.

- More than one assignment may be performed in a single statement.
- Function return values can be ignored when not needed.
- Typing is static, but weakly enforced: all data has a type, but implicit conversions may be performed.
- Declaration syntax mimics usage context. C has no "define" keyword; instead, a statement beginning with the name of a type is taken as a declaration. There is no "function" keyword; instead, a function is indicated by the parentheses of an argument list.
- User-defined (`typedef`) and compound types are possible.

6.1.2:C++ LANGUAGE

C++ is a general-purpose programming language. It has imperative, object-oriented and generic programming features, while also providing facilities for low-level memory manipulation.

It was designed with a bias toward system programming and embedded, resource-constrained and large systems, with performance, efficiency and flexibility of use as its design highlights. C++ has also been found useful in many other contexts, with key strengths being software infrastructure and resource-constrained applications, including desktop applications, servers (e.g. e-commerce, Web search or SQL servers), and performance-critical applications (e.g. telephone switches or space probes). C++ is a compiled language, with implementations of it available on many platforms. Many vendors provide C++ compilers, including the Free Software Foundation, Microsoft, Intel, and IBM.

The C++ language has two main components: a direct mapping of hardware features provided primarily by the C subset, and zero-overhead

abstractions based on those mappings. Stroustrup describes C++ as "a light-weight abstraction programming language [designed] for building and using efficient and elegant abstractions"; and "offering both hardware access and abstraction is the basis of C++. Doing it efficiently is what distinguishes it from other languages

Object storage

As in C, C++ supports four types of memory management: static storage duration objects, thread storage duration objects, automatic storage duration objects, and dynamic storage duration objects.

Static storage duration objects

Static storage duration objects are created before `main()` is entered (see exceptions below) and destroyed in reverse order of creation after `main()` exits.

Thread storage duration objects

Variables of this type are very similar to static storage duration objects. The main difference is the creation time is just prior to thread creation and destruction is done after the thread has been joined.

Automatic storage duration objects

The most common variable types in C++ are local variables inside a function or block, and temporary variables. The common feature about automatic variables is that they have a lifetime that is limited to the scope of the variable. They are created and potentially initialized at the point of declaration (see below for details) and destroyed in the *reverse* order of

creation when the scope is left. This is implemented by allocation on the stack.

Dynamic storage duration objects

These objects have a dynamic lifespan and are created with a call to new and destroyed explicitly with a call to delete

6.2 LIST OF MODULES

- Pre-processing
- Sobel Gradient operator
- Clustering
- Morphological process
- Segmentation
- Classification

6.3 MODULE DESCRIPTION

6.3.1 PREPROCESSING:

Image pre-processing is the term for operations on images at the lowest level of abstraction. These operations do not increase image information content but they decrease it if entropy is an information measure. The aim pre-processing is an improvement of the image data that suppresses undesired distortions or enhances some image features relevant for further processing and analysis task. The three methods occur in pre-processing occur

- Grayscale conversion
- Resizing
- Contrast enhancement

6.3.1.1 Grayscale conversion

The luminance of a pixel value of a grayscale image ranges from 0 to 255. The conversion of a color image into a grayscale image is converting the RGB values (24 bit) into grayscale value (8 bit).

6.3.1.2 Resizing

Image resizing is necessary when you need to increase or decrease the total number of pixels, whereas remapping can occur when you are correcting for lens distortion or rotating an image.

6.3.1.3 Contrast enhancement

Image enhancement techniques have been widely used in many applications of image processing where the subjective quality of images is important for human interpretation. Contrast is an important factor in any subjective evaluation of image quality. Contrast is created by the difference in luminance reflected from two adjacent surfaces. In other words, contrast is the difference in visual properties that makes an object distinguishable from other objects and the background. In visual perception, contrast is determined by the difference in the colour and brightness of the object with other objects.

6.3.2 Sobel gradient operator

The Sobel gradient operator is based on convolving the image with a small, separable, and integer-valued filter in the horizontal and vertical directions and is therefore relatively inexpensive in terms of

computations. On the other hand, the gradient approximation that it produces is relatively crude, in particular for high-frequency variations in the image. The sobel operator is used in the edge detection algorithm.

-1	0	+1
-2	0	+2
-1	0	+1

Gx

+1	+2	+1
0	0	0
-1	-2	-1

Gy

6.3.3 CLUSTERING:

Clustering is the task of grouping a set of objects in such a way that objects in the same group are more similar to each other than to those in other groups.

6.3.3.1 K-means clustering

K-means clustering is a method of vector quantisation, originally from signal processing, that is popular for cluster analysis. Aim is to partition n observations into k clusters in which each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean serving as a prototype of the cluster.

6.3.4 MORPHOLOGICAL PROCESS :

Morphology is a broad set of image processing operations that process images based on shapes. Morphological operations apply a structuring element to an input image, creating an output image of the same size. The most basic morphological operations are dilation and erosion.

6.3.4.1 Dilation

Dilation adds pixels to the boundaries of objects in an image. The number of pixels added or removed from the objects in an image depends on the size and shape of the *structuring element* used to process the image. The state of any given pixel in the output image is determined by applying a rule to the corresponding pixel and its neighbors in the input image.

RULE: The value of the output pixel is the *maximum* value of all the pixels in the input pixel's neighborhood. In a binary image, if any of the pixels is set to the value 1, the output pixel is set to 1.

6.3.4.2 Erosion

Erosion removes pixels on object boundaries. The number of pixels added or removed from the objects in an image depends on the size and shape of the *structuring element* used to process the image. The state of any given pixel in the output image is determined by applying a rule to the corresponding pixel and its neighbors in the input image.

RULE: The value of the output pixel is the *minimum* value of all the pixels in the input pixel's neighborhood. In a binary image, if any of the pixels is set to 0, the output pixel is set to 0.

6.3.4 CLASSIFICATION :

Classification is the process related to categorization, the process in which ideas and objects are recognized, differentiated and understood.

6.3.4.1 RNN classifier

RNN classifier is used to classify among the predicted text and dataset. RNN works on the principle of saving the output of a layer and feeding this back to the input in order to predict the output of the layer. RNN considers the current input and also the previously received inputs. It can memorize previous inputs due to its internal memory. RNN can handle sequential data. In RNN, the previous states is fed as input to the current state of the network. RNN can be used in NLP, Time Series Prediction, Machine Translation, etc.

There are 4 types of RNN namely:

1. One to One
2. One to Many
3. Many to One and
4. Many to Many.

6.3.5 SEGMENTATION:

Segmentation is the process of partitioning a digital image into multiple segments. It is used to simplify to change the representation of an image into something that is more meaningful and easier to analyze. Image segmentation is typically used to locate objects and boundaries images. More precisely, image segmentation is the process of assigning a label to every pixel in an image such that pixels with the same label share certain characteristics.

The result of image segmentation is a set of segments that collectively cover the entire image, or a set of contours extracted from the image . Each

of the pixels in a region are similar with respect to some characteristic or computed property, such as color, intensity, or texture. Adjacent regions are significantly different with respect to the same characteristic

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 Introduction

Testing is one of the important steps in the software development phase. Testing is a set of activities that can be planned in advance and conducted systematically. It is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. The goal of the testing during the phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself.

Purpose of Testing

- To verify the interaction between objects.
- To verify the proper integration of all components of the software.
- To verify that all requirements have been correctly implemented.
- To identify and ensure defects.

7.2 Levels of Testing

The various levels of testing are:

1. Unit Testing
2. Functional Testing
3. Performance Test
4. Stress Test
5. Structure Test
6. Integration Testing
7. White box Testing

8. Black box Testing

7.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional testing cases involved exercising the code with nominal input values for which the expected results are known, as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files.

7.2.3 Performance Test

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput, and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.2.4 Stress Test

Stress Test is those test designed to intentionally break the unit. A Great deal can be learned about the strength and limitations of

a program by examining the manner in which a programmer in which a program unit breaks.

7.2.5 Structured Test

Structured Tests are concerned with exercising the internal logic of a program and traversing particular execution paths. The way in which White-Box test strategy was employed to ensure that the test cases could Guarantee that all independent paths within a module have been have been exercised at least once.

- Exercise all logical decisions on their true or false sides.
- Execute all loops at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- Exercise internal data structures to assure their validity.
- Checking attributes for their correctness.
- Handling end of file condition, I/O errors, buffer problems and textual errors in output information

7.2.6 Integration Testing

Integration testing is a systematic technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. i.e., integration testing is the complete testing of the set of modules which makes up the product. The objective is to take untested modules and build a program structure tester should identify critical modules. Critical modules should be tested as early as possible. One approach is to wait until all the units have passed testing, and then combine them

and then tested. This approach is evolved from unstructured testing of small programs. Another strategy is to construct the product in increments of tested units. A small set of modules are integrated together and tested, to which another module is found and corrected.

7.2.7 White Box Testing

White Box testing of the program code of the functions shows that the modules are stable at normal conditions and are efficient then the existing system in their stability and efficiency as such as in the motion detection module that access likely in existing systems.

7.2.8 Black Box Testing

Black box testing shows that every module of the software work as expected and produced the outputs likely. The functionality tests such as in the 3 modules are sampled and tested individually.

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The character recognition and detection approach is been proposed in this paper.It is used to extract the text from the complex images.In the previous paper the text is been detected using the OCR.In our proposed system we are detecting the text from the image.The image is initially been enhanced if it is of low quality.Enhanced image edge is been detected using sobel operator.Then grouping of similar datatypes is done.RNN classifier is used for the comparison between segmented text and dataset values.

The text is detected more accurately from the existing system.Additionally,in this proposed system the detected text is given as an audio output for visually impaired.The audio can be replayed many times as per the wish.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed an artificial neural network based character recognition system for recognition of English alphanumeric characters. Our system produces very good result for individual classes but produces satisfactory result when the classes are combined together.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The method described in this work cannot distinguish between text and non-text in the image. The character extraction approach described in the work is unable to extract characters for those languages in which characters are connected to form words. In the future, we plan to work for Tamil Character Recognition since Tamil is our mother language.

APPENDICES

A.SOURCE CODE:

```
function varargout = guidemo(varargin)
% GUIDEMO MATLAB code for guidemo.fig
%   GUIDEMO, by itself, creates a new GUIDEMO or raises the existing
%   singleton*.
%
%   H = GUIDEMO returns the handle to a new GUIDEMO or the handle
to
%   the existing singleton*.
%
%   GUIDEMO('CALLBACK',hObject,eventData,handles,...) calls the
local
%   function named CALLBACK in GUIDEMO.M with the given input
arguments.
%
%   GUIDEMO('Property','Value',...) creates a new GUIDEMO or raises
the
%   existing singleton*. Starting from the left, property value pairs are
%   applied to the GUI before guidemo_OpeningFcn gets called. An
%   unrecognized property name or invalid value makes property
application
%   stop. All inputs are passed to guidemo_OpeningFcn via varargin.
%
%   *See GUI Options on GUIDE's Tools menu. Choose "GUI allows
only one
```

```

% instance to run (singleton)".
%
% See also: GUIDE, GUIDATA, GUIHANDLES

% Edit the above text to modify the response to help guidemo

% Last Modified by GUIDE v2.5 18-Feb-2019 17:23:38

% Begin initialization code - DO NOT EDIT
gui_Singleton = 1;
gui_State = struct('gui_Name',    mfilename, ...
                  'gui_Singleton', gui_Singleton, ...
                  'gui_OpeningFcn', @guidemo_OpeningFcn, ...
                  'gui_OutputFcn', @guidemo_OutputFcn, ...
                  'gui_LayoutFcn', [] , ...
                  'gui_Callback', []);
if nargin && ischar(varargin{1})
    gui_State.gui_Callback = str2func(varargin{1});
end

if nargout
    [varargout{1:nargout}] = gui_mainfcn(gui_State, varargin{:});
else
    gui_mainfcn(gui_State, varargin{:});
end
% End initialization code - DO NOT EDIT

```

```

% --- Executes just before guidemo is made visible.
function guidemo_OpeningFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles, varargin)
% This function has no output args, see OutputFcn.
% hObject    handle to figure
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
% varargin   command line arguments to guidemo (see VARARGIN)

% Choose default command line output for guidemo
handles.output = hObject;

handles.output = hObject;

a=ones([256 256]);
axes(handles.axes2);imshow(a);
axes(handles.axes3);imshow(a);
axes(handles.axes4);imshow(a);

% Update handles structure
guidata(hObject, handles);

% UIWAIT makes guidemo wait for user response (see UIRESUME)
% uiwait(handles.figure1);

% --- Outputs from this function are returned to the command line.

```

```

function varargout = guidemo_OutputFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% varargout cell array for returning output args (see VARARGOUT);
% hObject handle to figure
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Get default command line output from handles structure
varargout{1} = handles.output;

```

```

function edit1_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to edit1 (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of edit1 as text
% str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of edit1 as a double

```

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all properties.

```

function edit1_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to edit1 (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles empty - handles not created until after all CreateFcns called

% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on Windows.

```

```

% See ISPC and COMPUTER.
if ispc && isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end

% --- Executes on button press in Speak.
function Speak_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to Speak (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% a=get(handles.edit1,'String')
recognizedText=handles.recognizedText;
tts(recognizedText);

% Update handles structure
guidata(hObject, handles);

% --- Executes on button press in classify.
function classify_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to classify (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
% [filename, pathname] = uigetfile('*..*', 'Pick a image file');

```

```

%   if isequal(filename,0) || isequal(pathname,0)
%       disp('User pressed cancel')
%   else
%       disp(['User selected ', fullfile(pathname, filename)])
%       file=imread(filename);
% %       axes(handles.axes1);
global file
% file=handles.file;
axes(handles.axes3);
    imshow(file);
    ocrResults=ocr(file);
    recognizedText=ocrResults.Text;
    testdat{ 1 }=recognizedText;
    set(handles.resultbox,'String',recognizedText);
    xlswrite('new.xlsx',testdat)

handles.recognizedText=recognizedText;

% Update handles structure
guidata(hObject, handles);

% --- Executes on button press in browse.
function browse_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to browse (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB

```

```

% handles  structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
global im
cd images
[file,path] = uigetfile('*.jpg;*.bmp;*.gif;*.png', 'Pick an Image File');
im = imread(file);
cd ..
axes(handles.axes2);
imshow(im,[]);
% im(handles)=im;

guidata(hObject, handles);

```

```

% --- Executes on button press in Pre_processing.

```

```

Function Pre_processing_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)

```

```

% hObject  handle to Pre_processing (see GCBO)

```

```

% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB

```

```

% handles  structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

```

```

global im

```

```

global file

```

```

% im = handles.im;

```

```

inp=imresize(im,[512 512]);

```

```
if size(inp,3)>1
    inp = rgb2gray(inp);
end
file=inp;

axes(handles.axes4);
imshow(file,[]);

% file.handles=file;

guidata(hObject, handles);
```

B.SCREENSHOTS

Matlab 2014:

Initial Screen:

Choosing the Image:

Image is Inserted:

After GrayScale Conversion:

The diagram illustrates a four-step process for image processing:

- Browse**: A button to select an image.
- pre processing**: A button to convert the image to grayscale. This step is shown with two side-by-side images: the original color image and its grayscale version. Both images contain the text: "THE BEAUTIFUL THING ABOUT FEAR IS, WHEN YOU RUN TO IT, IT RUNS AWAY." - ROBIN SHARMA.
- classify**: A button to perform classification on the grayscale image.
- Speak**: A button to output the result.

The final output is labeled *Result* and is represented by a large white square placeholder.

After RNN Classification:

Audio Output:

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